

THE ULOBORIDAE OF SOUTH AFRICA

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ABSTRACT

The family Uloboridae is represented by 19 genera and 287 species, with a wide distribution throughout the tropical and subtropical regions. From South Africa 4 genera and 9 species are known but none of them have been revised. Seven of the species have a wide distribution and are listed as Least Concern only two species are Data Deficient. Keys to the subfamilies and *Miagrammopes* species are provided.

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Miagrammopes constrictus female

Photo Vida van der Walt

* Species from South Africa but not listed in World Spider Catalog (2020)

Note 1: Wrongly listed in World Spider Catalog (2020) from South Africa.

Note 2: Presence of *Zosis* sp. in South Africa still to be confirmed

FAMILY ULOBORIDAE Thorell, 1869

The family Uloboridae is represented by 19 genera and 287 species, with a wide distribution (World Spider Catalog 2020). From South Africa 4 genera and 9 species are known.

COMMON NAMES: Venomless Spiders

MORPHOLOGY: Body size: 3-10 mm (males more slender). Colour: body usually dull shades of cream, grey or brown some species white. Carapace either long and narrow (*Miagrammopes*), pear-shaped (*Uloborus*) or more triangular (*Hyptiotes*); eyes 8 in 2 rows (4:4) but anterior eye row reduced in *Miagrammopes*. Abdomen slender or with 1-2 humps (*Hyptiotes* and *Uloborus*); or very narrow and elongate, sometimes extending past spinnerets (*Miagrammopes*). Legs I and IV longer than rest of legs in *Uloborus* and *Miagrammopes*, while the legs are shorter and stouter in *Hyptiotes*; tibiae I with brush of long setae in *Uloborus plumipes*.

LIFESTYLE: They spin orb-webs made of cribellate silk or adapted orb-webs. Their webs are usually made between the leaves of plants. *Hyptiotes* is found in the warmer humid regions while *Miagrammopes* and *Uloborus* are found widely distributed throughout most biomes. Characteristic behaviour of all the uloborids are the front legs are extended while in the web. In the webs of both *Hyptiotes* and *Miagrammopes* is the use of a single, resting thread that is held under tension and manipulated by the spider when catching prey. In *Miagrammopes* a horizontal, usually single line is made between two branches or twigs with only the central section consisting of cribellate silk. In *Hyptiotes* a web is produced that resembles a fragment of a complete orb-web but it consists only of four radii. Uloborids lack venom glands but pour digestive enzymes onto the prey to kill it. The silk wrapped around the prey becomes transparent after absorbing some of the enzymes. The spiders do not use their chelicerae while wrapping the prey. Several uloborid species have a cosmopolitan distribution and are frequently found in and around houses, with the following species recorded from South Africa: *Uloborus plumipes* Lucas, *U. walckenaerius* Latreille and *Zosis geniculata* Olivier.

TAXONOMY: African genera not revised.

Hyptiotes akermani female

Photo Peter Webb

Miagrammopes constrictus female

Photo Peter Webb

Uloborus plumipes female

Photo Peter Webb

KEY TO THE SUBFAMILIES

1. Body much longer than wide with the sides almost parallel (A); carapace rectangular, much longer than wide, sides almost parallel (B); anterior eyes reduced or absent; sternum divided (C); legs I and IV much longer than rest; the web a single line or a simple web with a few threads (D)

.....**MIAGRAMMOPINAE**

- Body and legs not as above**2**

2. Body more oval in shape (E); carapace pear-shaped (F); abdomen usually with one hump or two (E); leg I in some species (females) with tufts of hair on tibiae, in males with 2-3 rows of strong spines; leg I longer and stronger than the rest; orb-web usually horizontally positioned (G).....

.....**ULOBORINAE**

- Body oval in shape (H); the carapace modified as wide in the middle as it is long (I); legs shorter and thicker than in subfamilies above; web triangular in shape, only a sector of an orb-web (J)

.....**HYPTIOTINAE**

GENUS *HYPTIOTES* Walckenaer, 1837

The genus *Hyptiotes* Walckenaer, 1837 is represented by 16 spp. with only one recorded from Africa. The endemic South African species *Hyptiotes akermani* (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAME: Triangle-web Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Hyptiotes paradoxus* C. Koch, 1834

MORPHOLOGY: Body size TL female and male 3-5 mm. Carapace as broad as long; weakly convex above, highest and broadest at second eye row, carapace narrowed and rounded in front and widely rounded posteriorly; eight eyes; arranged in two unequal, transverse rows; anterior row procurved as seen from in front, nearly straight in dorsal view; median eyes close together and very small lateral eyes widely separated from medians; much wider posterior eye row recurved, with large median eyes as widely separated as anterior lateral eyes, clypeus broad, sloping; sternum triangular, considerably longer than wide, truncated and widest in front, quite evenly tapering behind to blunt point between slightly separated posterior coxae. Abdomen of females sub-oval, moderately to strongly arched; abdomen of males more slender; anterior spinnerets much larger than posterior pair. Legs short and stout; legs of females without spines, except for few on ventral surface of metatarsi; legs of males longer, with dorsal and lateral spines; calamistrum occupying most of length of flattened fourth metatarsus and consisting of single series of curved bristles.

LIFESTYLE: *Hyptiotes* produces a rudimentary orb-web consisting only of four radii connected to a single thread which the spider uses to manipulate the web. This triangular web is made between leaves on plants (Lubin, 1986). The egg-sac is flattened, mottled brown in colour and attached to the surface of a twig (Lawrence (1964, Dippenaar-Schoeman & Hadad 2014; Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013)).

TAXONOMY: Only one species is presently known, but more than 40 specimens, housed in the National Collection of Arachnida, have been collected from four provinces in South Africa. They differ in appearance and more species are expected.

Hyptiotes akermani Photo: P. Webb

From Wakefield Photo: P. Webb

Hyptiotes akermani female showing the calamistrum on leg IV Photo: ASD

From Addo NP Photo: L. Wiese

Hyptiotes akermani Wiehle, 1964

COMMON NAME: Ackerman's Triangle-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Wiehle (1964) from Ifafa Beach in KwaZulu-Natal. The species has a wide distribution and was sampled from four provinces (EOO=320 914 km²; AOO=52km²; 1-1706 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: *Hyptiotes* make a reduced orb-web. The web produced resembles a fragment of a complete orb-web but it consists only of four radii. The spider rests on the single thread upon which the four radii converge. This single, resting thread is held under tension and is manipulated by the spider when catching prey. The webs are made in vegetation and they are sampled in the Forest, Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Hogsback (-32.59, 26.92); Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72); Mkambati Nature Reserve (-31.32, 29.97). **Gauteng:** Dinokeng (-25.4, 28.38). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Cathedral Peak (-28.94, 29.19); Ifafa Beach (-30.45, 30.64); Loteni Nature Reserve (-29.47, 29.52); Pongola (Farm Vergeval) (-27.35, 31.61); Midlands, Good Hope plantation, Boston (-29.651, 29.976); Wakefield Farm (-29.473, 29.893). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Lhuvhodo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.95, 29.87); Roodewal Forest (-23.02, 30.03); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve, Farm Malta (-24.17, 30.25).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: No known threats. Species presently protected in several protected areas such as: Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoenan et al. 2020), Mkambati Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2011); Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2018); Lhuvhodo Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2008) and Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2016). More sampling needed to collect the male.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female.

Epigyne after Wiehle (1964)

Hyptiotes showing the feathery setae
Photo ASD

Hyptiotes akermani from Dinokeng Photo: P. Webb

Hyptiotes akermani from Addo NP Photo: Linda

GENUS *MIAGRAMMOPES* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1870

The genus *Miagrammopes* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1870 is represented by 69 species with three species known from South Africa (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAME: Single-Line Web Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Miagrammopes thwaitesi* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1870

MORPHOLOGY: Carapace longer than wide; low; weakly convex above; cephalic region broad; obtusely rounded in front; thoracic region with nearly subparallel sides, truncated behind; eyes unequal in size and arranged in two unequal transverse rows; eyes of front row minute or obsolete; evidence of anterior median eyes is seen in small, dark pigment spots of some specimens; posterior row recurved, with median eyes widely separated; clypeus broad, sloping, equal in width to two or more diameters of posterior median eye; sternum elongated, divided into two unequal sternites seemingly joined to carapace between second and third coxae by narrow sclerites. Abdomen elongated, often tubular; calamistrum broad lobe, with spinning field entire. Leg formula 1423; legs quite long and unequal, with second and third pairs short and thin; fourth pair long, laterally compressed, and first pair stoutest and longest, with apical segments laterally compressed; trochanters of first and fourth legs strongly developed, exceeding coxae in length; metatarsus IV laterally compressed, with ventral comb of short spines; calamistrum occupying most of length of compressed fourth metatarsus and consisting of single, sinuous series of curved bristles set on thin keel on dorsum of segment; front tibiae of males often with rows of stout spines.

LIFESTYLE: *Miagrammopes* species construct a horizontal, usually single thread between two branches or twigs. The spider lays down a thick band of viscid silk and then takes up a position upside down near a point of attachment, only the central section consisting of cribellated silk. The thread has one or a few sticky capture threads attached to it that are held under tension (Lubin et al. 1978). The line is kept under tension and released with a snap when prey alights on the inviting line and becomes entangled. The attack behaviour involves rapid jerking and sudden sagging of the capture thread (Akerman 1932). In some tropical species, such as *M. brevicauda*, the web consists of three threads (Peters 1983). The spider positions itself at the end of one of the upper threads and only approaches the mid-section in darkness. According to Opell (1984), the female carries the cylindrical egg-sac until the spiderlings emerge.

TAXONOMY: African species not revised.

Miagrammopes sp. female Photo Vida van der Walt

Miagrammopes sp. female showing handling of silk threads Photo Peter Webb

KEY TO MIAGRAMMOPES SPECIES

Three species presently known from South Africa

1. Abdomen tail-like extending past the spinnerets (A).....*M. longicaudus*
 - Abdomen not tail-like.....2
2. Female recognized by 6 black spots on abdomen(B); metatarsi 1 with thick mane of setae
 -*M. constrictus*
 - Female recognized by abdomen with central black marking (C); setae on leg I different
 -*M. brevidaudus*

Constantia Cape Town Irene Roodeplaat Mphaphuli Tarsi leg 1

***Miagrammopes constrictus* females Photo Peter Webb**

MooiNooi Kloof Tarsi leg 1 Lekgalameetse

***Miagrammopes brevidaudus* females Photo Peter Webb**

Miagrammopes brevicaudus O.P.-Cambridge, 1882

COMMON NAME: Two-spotted Single-Line Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic species described by O.P.-Cambridge (1882) with the type locality given only as Caffraria. The species is recorded also from Swaziland. In South Africa recorded from seven provinces and (EEO=726 654 km²; AOO=120 km²; 15-1758 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: They make a horizontal web, usually a single line is made between two branches or twigs, with only the central section consisting of cribellate silk. The web has one or a few sticky capture threads that are held under tension and released when prey is close to the line. The attack behaviour consists of rapid jerking and sudden sagging of the catch thread. The spider rests at the end of one of the lines and will only approach the centre as darkness sets in. The webs are made in vegetation and the species has been sampled from all the floral biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Swaziland and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72); Kei River Mouth (-32.68, 28.37). **Gauteng:** Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.8, 28.77); Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Roodeplaat Research Station (-25.66, 28.35); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Walter Sisulu National Botanical Garden (-26.14, 27.86); MooNooi. **KwaZulu-Natal:** Cathedral Peak (-28.94, 29.19); iSimangaliso Wetland Park: False Bay Park (-27.92, 32.27); Mlawula Nature Reserve (-26.22, 32); Monks Cowl (-29.03, 29.4); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); iSimangaliso Wetland Park Mkhuzi Game Reserve (-27.6, 32.02). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.95, 29.87); Mabula Nature Reserve (-24.84, 27.96); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Sovenga Hill (-23.88, 29.73); Wolkberg Nature Reserve (-23.94, 29.95); Rhemardo Naboomspruit (-24.52, 28.70); Luvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve, Farm Balloon (-24.2, 30.34); Marakele National Park (-24.41, 27.64). **Mpumalanga:** Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96); Kruger National Park, Pretoriuskop, Shabeni (-25.123, 31.237). **North-West:** Kgawane Mountain Reserve (-25.72, 27.18).

Miagrammopes brevicaudus female from Kloof Photo Peter Webb

Miagrammopes brevicaudus female from MooiNooi Photo Peter Webb

Calamistrum on leg 4

Setae leg 1

Miagrammopes brevicaudus (continued)

Western Cape: Anysberg Nature Reserve (-33.53, 20.76); De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Table Mountain National Park (-34.52, 18.76)

CONSERVATION MEASURES: More sampling is needed to collect the male but there are no significant threats to this species. Presently protected in the following areas: Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020), Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad et al. 2009), Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019), Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2009), Luvhondo Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2008) and Marakele National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known only from female.

Miagrammopes brevicaudus female from Kloof Photo Peter Webb

Miagrammopes brevicaudus female from MooiNooi Photo Peter Webb

Miagrammopes constrictus Purcell, 1904

COMMON NAME: six-spotted Single-Line Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Purcell (1904) from Durban. The species has been sampled from seven provinces (EOO=345 880 km²; AOO=40 km²; 17-1513 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is therefore listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: The webs are made in vegetation and this species has been sampled from the Grassland, Nama Karoo and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Mountain Zebra National Park (-32.24, 25.43); Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72); Thyspunt, 12 km WNW, Cape St Francis (-34.206, 24.708). **Gauteng:** Irene (Smuts House)(-25.89, 28.23). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.1); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Vryheid Nature Reserve (-27.75, 30.79); Richards Bay (-28.78, 32.10); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24). **Limpopo:** Tshulu (Venda) (-22.58, 30.81); Pafuri (Waller's Camp) (-22.424, 30.911); Entabeni Forest Reserve (-23.00, 30.23); Kruger National Park, Shingwedzi (20km SE) (-23.22, 31.56); Luvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Springbok Flats: Tuinplaas (-24.9, 28.73). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park Skukuza (-24.989, 31.593); Kruger National Park, Pretoriuskop, Shabeni (-25.15, 31.2). **North West:** Rustenburg Nature Reserve (-25.72, 27.18). **Western Cape:** Constantia (-33.93, 18.38).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is protected in several protected areas such as Mountain Zebra National Park, Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020), Hluhluwe Nature Reserve, Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad et al. 2009) and Vryheid Nature Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised known only from the female. Female recognized by the mane of setae on tarsi I and abdomen with six black spots.

Thick mane of setae on tarsi I

Epigyne after Lehtinen (1967)

Miagrammopes constrictus female from Constantia Cape

Miagrammopes constrictus female from Irene Photo Peter Webb

Miagrammopes longicaudus O.P.-Cambridge, 1882

COMMON NAME: Long-tailed Single-Line Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by O.P.-Cambridge (1882) from Caffraria. In South Africa it is only known from the type locality. Due to the lack of data the status of the species is undetermined and therefore listed as Data Deficient.

DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

LIFESTYLE: Unknown

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Caffraria. (Caffraria' was a name given first to southern Africa, then to Xhosaland (area between the Kei and Keiskamma rivers) and subsequently to the Eastern Cape Province situated No exact locality.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Types need to be re-examined and redescribed. More sampling needed.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known from both sexes but poorly described.

Miagrammopes longicaudus Photo: SANSA VM

Miagrammopes longicaudus female after O.P.-Cambridge (1882)

Miagrammopes longicaudus male palp after Opell (1984)

GENUS *PHILOPONELLA* Mello-Leitão, 1917

The genus *Philoponella*, represented by 41 species was described by Mello-Leitão (1917). The genus has a worldwide distribution with only two species recorded from Africa (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAME: Philoponella Hackled Orb-Web Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Philoponella republicana* (Simon, 1891)

MORPHOLOGY: Body size TL: females 4.6-8.2 mm, and males from 3.8 mm. to 4.1 mm. Colour specimens quite white, with faint, dusky spots on abdominal tubercles Carapace longer than wide; pale with broad dusky side stripes; eyes small; posterior row almost straight; integument clothed with white setae. Abdomen with front anterior tubercles distinct, posterior tubercles less distinct, and apex of abdomen nearly in middle of length.

LIFESTYLE: Web dwellers.

TAXONOMY: African species not revised. Status still unsure.

Philoponella sp. Photo Walter Juber

Philoponella sp. Photo Linda Wiese

Philoponella angolensis (Lessert, 1933)

COMMON NAME: Angola Hackled Orb-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic species described BY Lessert (1933) from Angola. The species has been sampled from three African countries. In South Africa sampled from four provinces (EOO=501 125 km²; AOO=32 km²; 0-894 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range, the species is therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: An orb-web spider making their web with cribellated silk in vegetation. Sampled from Fynbos, Savanna and Thicket biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Ivory Coast, Angola, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Jeffrey's Bay (-34.06, 24.91); Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72); King William's Town (-32.88, 27.39); Thornhill (-33.89, 25.14). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Tembe Elephant Park (-27.034, 32.425); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.544, 32.155). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04). **Western Cape:** Gouritsmond (Borrelfontein) (-34.34, 21.87).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in the Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020), Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad et al. 2010), Ndumo Game Reserve and Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised known from both sexes.

Philoponella angolensis male Photo Linda Wiese

Philoponella angolensis male Photo Linda Wiese

Philoponella operosa (Simon, 1896)

COMMON NAME: Cape Hackled Orb-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Simon (1896) as *Uloborus operosus* with type locality given only as “Colonie du Cap”. The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for unknown provenance and taxonomic reasons.

LIFESTYLE: Unknown.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, know only from female, not illustrated. Status of species still unsure.

Philoponella operosa from Addo NP Photo Linda Wiese

Philoponella operosa Photo ASD

GENUS *ULOBORUS* Latreille, 1806

The genus *Uloborus* is a large genus represented by 80 species and subspecies of which six have been reported from the Afrotropical Region (World Spider Catalog 2020).

COMMON NAME: Hackled Orb-Web Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Uloborus walckenaerius* Latreille, 1806

COMMON NAME: Hackled Orb-Web Spiders

MORPHOLOGY: Body size TL males and females: 4–6 mm. Colour of body usually dull shades of cream, grey or brown usually with markings. Carapace pear-shaped; with cephalic and thoracic regions of females level, thoracic depression a shallow pit; cephalic region of males curved slightly downward from thoracic depression; eyes: eight in two rows (4:4); both eye rows recurved. Abdomen longer than wide with 1–2 humps. Legs II and IV longer than the other legs; tibiae I with brush of long setae in some species.

LIFESTYLE: They build small orb-webs with cribellated silk. The hub is often meshed or strengthened with a stabilimentum that varies in shape. The most common stabilimentum configuration seems to be a linear silk band. The web is usually tugged forcefully as the spider approaches the prey to locate it and entangle it further. The first, and to a lesser extent, the second legs are used for tugging. The front legs are used to lightly touch the prey. Hanging from the first and second legs, the spider uses the fourth pair of legs to throw silk onto the prey to subdue it. The spider faces away from the prey while wrapping it. The silk entangles the thrashing limbs, preventing injury to the spider. They prey on a variety of flying insects. Uloborids lack venom glands and use digestive enzymes that are poured onto the prey to kill them. The silk wrapped around the prey becomes transparent after absorbing some of the enzymes. Spiders are frequently seen with the large prey mass in their mouth.

Uloborus plumipes female in web showing the linear stabilimentum Photo Vida van der Walt

Uloborus plumipes female in web with large prey mass covered with translucent silk Photo Hannes Mitchell

Uloborus planipedi Simon, 1896

COMMON NAME: Hackled Orb-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic species described by Simon (1896) from Port Elizabeth. In South Africa collected from five provinces (EEO=554 505 km²; AOO=48 km²; 7-1513 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is therefore listed as Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: An orb-web spider making the web with cribellated silk in vegetation in the Forest, Grassland, Nama Karoo and Savanna biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Mountain Zebra National Park (-32.24, 25.43); Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72); Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Wakefield Farm (-29.473, 29.893). **Limpopo:** Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Limpopo Valley Nature Reserve (-22.22, 29.13); Ratombobo Forest (-23.06, 30.17); Venetia, Limpopo Reserve (-22.321, 29.324). **Western Cape:** Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to this species. Protected in areas such as Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020), Karoo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 1999), Mountain Zebra National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2006), Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al, 2006) and Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known only from the female, not illustrated.

Uloborus planipedi female Photo Linda Wiese

Uloborus plumipes Lucas, 1846

COMMON NAME: Feather- Legged Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An old world species described by Lucas (1846) that is known throughout Africa. In South Africa it has a very wide distribution and has been recorded from all the provinces (EOO=925 049 km²; AOO=212 km²; 6-1762 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range, the species is therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: They are web dwellers making an orb-web. This species is very common in the country and is frequently found in and around houses. They were sampled from most of the floral biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013) as well as from crops such as avocado, citrus, cotton, pistachio, prickly pear, strawberries and tomatoes (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Old World, Argentina (introduced). In South Africa (9 provinces).

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Jeffrey's Bay (-34.06, 24.91); Middelburg (-31.49, 24.99); Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72). **Free State:** Bethlehem (-28.23, 28.3); Mpetsane Conservation Estate (near Clocolan) (-28.8, 27.65); Vrede (-27.43, 29.13); Bloemfontein National Botanical Gardens (-29.02, 26.12); Luckhoff district, Farm Bankfontein (-29.73, 24.77). **Gauteng:** Baviaanspoort (-25.67, 28.37); Benoni (-26.19, 28.31); Centurion (-25.85, 28.16); Johannesburg (-26.2, 28.04); Kempton Park (-26.09, 28.23); Kloofendal Nature Reserve (-26.14, 27.86); Modderfontein (-26.08, 28.17); Pretoria National Botanical Garden (-25.74, 28.19); Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Pretoria/Tshwane (Rietondale Research Station) (-25.73, 28.23); Randburg (-26.07, 27.92); Rietveldam Nature Reserve (-25.85, 28.16); Roodeplaat Research Station (-25.66, 28.35); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Roodepoort (-26.14, 27.86); Villieria, Pretoria (-25.71, 28.23); Wallmannsthal (-25.52, 28.3); Wonderboom (-25.68, 28.2). **KwaZulu-Natal:** ISimangaliso Wetland Park: Hell's Gate (-28, 32.48); Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87); Mkuzi Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Newcastle district, Ncandu Falls (-27.51, 29.50). **Limpopo:** Abel Erasmus Pass, near Mogoba (-24.46, 30.61); Entabeni Nature Reserve (-22.99, 30.26); Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Lhuvhodo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Limpopo Valley Nature Reserve (-22.22, 29.13); Mabula Nature Reserve (-24.84, 27.96); Pafuri Camp (-22.42, 30.91); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Pietersburg/Polokwane (-23.89, 29.46); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Thabazimbi (-24.6, 27.38); Tshulu (Venda) (-22.58, 30.81); Welgevonden Nature Reserve (-24.39, 27.78).

After Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocque 1997

Uloborus plumipes female lateral view Photo Vida vd Walt

Uloborus plumipes female lateral view Photo Peter Webb

Uloborus plumipes Photo H. Mitchell

Uloborus plumipes Photo H. Mitchell

***Uloborus plumipes* (continued)**

Mpumalanga: Burgers Hall (-25.02, 31.08); Loskop Dam Nature Reserve (-25.46, 29.23); Louw's Creek (-25.79, 31.04); Lowveld National Botanical Gardens (-25.47, 31); Marble Hall (-24.96, 29.29). **North West:** Hartebeespoort Experimental Farm (-25.6, 27.82); Kroondal (-25.75, 27.32); Olifantsnek dam (-25.8, 27.25); Wolmaransstad (-27.19, 25.97). **Northern Cape:** Augrabies National Park (-28.53, 20.29); Prieska (Green Valley Nuts Estate) (-29.68, 22.74). **Western Cape:** Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Oudtshoorn (-33.59, 22.21); Swartberg Nature Reserve (Gamkaskloof) (-33.35, 21.67).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species It is protected in more than 17 protected areas.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Know from both sexes.

Uloborus plumipes female lateral view Photo Clarissa de Lange

Uloborus plumipes female in web Photo Allen Jones

Uloborus plumipes female in web Photo Peter Webb

Uloborus walckenaerius Latreille, 1806

COMMON NAME: Fluffy Hackled Orb-Web Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A species described by Latreille (1806) with a wide distribution throughout the Palearctic region. It has also been sampled from a few localities in South Africa (EOO=149 075 km²; AOO=24 km²; 357-1399 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide global geographical range, the species is therefore listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: Orb-web dweller.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Palearctic. New: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Amanzi Private Game Reserve (-28.62, 26.68); Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22); Tussen die Riviere Nature Reserve (-30.47, 25.19); National Botanical Gardens, Bloemfontein (-29.05, 26.21). **Northern Cape:** Tswalu Game Reserve (-27.30, 22.44). **Western Cape:** Oudtshoorn (-33.59, 22.21).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Introduced species. Know from both sexes, illustrated.

Uloborus walckenaerius female Photo Les Oates

female Photo Les Oates

Uloborus walckenaerius female Photo Ant West

UNDETERMINED SPECIES

***Uloborus* sp.**

Pretoria Koos Geldenhuys

Ndumu GR Charles Haddad

Bloemfontein J. van Zyl

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